

Research Article

Cozy Wrap: The Eco-Marine Sleeping Solution

Nur Yasmin Abdul Razak¹, Nurul Fatin Hasinah Saibon², Sabrina Jin Shamsudin³, Najwahanis Aisyah Ahmad Amir⁴, Nur Anis Yasmin Talib⁵, Nurul Ain Syazreen Norulhisham⁶, Nur Izzah Atirah Mohd Aziz⁷ and Sharir Aizat Kamaruddin^{8*}

¹ Faculty of Applied Sciences, Universiti Teknologi MARA, Cawangan Perlis, Kampus Arau, Perlis, Malaysia; 2023299544@student.uitm.edu.my

² Faculty of Applied Sciences, Universiti Teknologi MARA, Cawangan Perlis, Kampus Arau, Perlis, Malaysia; 2023491702@student.uitm.edu.my

³ Faculty of Applied Sciences, Universiti Teknologi MARA, Cawangan Perlis, Kampus Arau, Perlis, Malaysia; 2023414528@student.uitm.edu.my

⁴ Faculty of Applied Sciences, Universiti Teknologi MARA, Cawangan Perlis, Kampus Arau, Perlis, Malaysia; 2023601246@student.uitm.edu.my

⁵ Faculty of Applied Sciences, Universiti Teknologi MARA, Cawangan Perlis, Kampus Arau, Perlis, Malaysia; 2023465957@student.uitm.edu.my

⁶ Faculty of Applied Sciences, Universiti Teknologi MARA, Cawangan Perlis, Kampus Arau, Perlis, Malaysia; 2023698696@student.uitm.edu.my

⁷ Faculty of Applied Sciences, Universiti Teknologi MARA, Cawangan Perlis, Kampus Arau, Perlis, Malaysia; 2023820136@student.uitm.edu.my

⁸ Marine Research Station, Faculty of Applied Sciences, Universiti Teknologi MARA, Perlis Branch, Arau Campus, 02600 Arau, Perlis, Malaysia; shariraizat@uitm.edu.my

* Correspondence: shariraizat@uitm.edu.my, 0175611159

Abstract: *Eco-Marine Sleeping Solutions is the latest innovation in the world of outdoor sleeping gear, specially designed to meet the challenges of the cold and damp marine environment. A major problem facing sea enthusiasts and maritime travellers is the difficulty of obtaining warmth and comfort without relying on environmentally friendly electrical components or rechargeable energy sources. Cozy Wrap solves this problem by using a portable heating system based on natural and sustainable materials. This sleeping bag is made from marine recycled materials and comes with a biodegradable heat pack that can be activated as needed. The heat pack is housed in a strategic waterproof pocket, providing targeted warmth to critical body areas such as the legs, torso and back. In addition, the Cozy Wrap also has a waterproof and breathable outer layer, a rust-proof zipper, and an anti-microbial treatment to prevent the growth of fungi in humid conditions. This innovation is not only environmentally friendly but has high potential for commercialization, especially in the growing maritime equipment market. Cozy Wrap offers a practical and sustainable solution for marine enthusiasts who need a reliable product in challenging environments.*

Keywords: *Eco-Marine; Environmentally friendly, Portable Heating; Recycled Materials, Sleeping bag*

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1. INTRODUCTION

In the outdoor equipment industry, sleeping bags are one of the main components that ensure the comfort and safety of users, especially in extreme environments such as marine areas. The importance of a sleeping bag that can provide adequate thermal protection in cold weather conditions

has been recognized in previous studies from the United States. In the Marine Corps, an evaluation of the thermal protection capabilities of military sleeping bag modules indicated the need for innovation to meet the demands of a harsh environment (Hickey & Petersen, 1994). In addition, Zuo (2004) emphasized the factors that affect the thermal insulation value of the sleeping bag system and emphasized the importance of choosing the right material and design to ensure effectiveness in different weather conditions.

For this reason, Cozy Wrap has been developed as a solution that is not only environmentally friendly but also energy efficient. Warmth and humidity tolerance are important factors in cold and humid marine environments, as found in a study on the need for warmth to survive a mass rescue incident in the Arctic (Mak et al., 2011). Therefore, Cozy Wrap uses recycled ocean materials and biodegradable heat packs to keep users warm without relying on power or batteries. This innovation also considers aspects of environmental sustainability, in line with green design research that emphasizes the use of sustainable materials in products (Kim, 2010).

In this way, the Cozy Wrap not only functions as a normal sleeping bag but is also an innovation that reflects the friendliness of the environment, while offering maximum protection and comfort to the user in the harsh marine environment.

1.1 Objective

Cozy Wrap's main goal is to provide an effective and environmentally friendly heating solution for the marine environment with recycled materials and biodegradable thermal wraps. To achieve this goal, several specific objectives were developed:

1. To evaluate the effectiveness of the Cozy Wrap in providing adequate insulation and comfort to the user in cold and humid conditions.
2. To ensure that the materials used, including the fatty acids in the insulation layer, are of high quality, safe, and meet environmental sustainability standards.
3. To optimize manufacturing costs and market prices to ensure these products are competitive and affordable for consumers who need innovative and environmentally friendly heating solutions.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

2.1 Method

The development of this innovative product is described by referring to Figure 1.

Figure 1: Development of Cozy Wrap.

2.2 Materials

The Cozy Wrap is designed using carefully selected materials to ensure product quality and effectiveness in providing optimal warmth. The outer layer of this sleeping bag uses recycled polyester, which was chosen for its resistance to moisture and high strength, in line with green practices recommended in environmental design studies (Kim, 2010) and material durability standards in maritime-related studies (Mak et al., 2011).

For the inner layer, organic cotton is used because of its soft, breathable, and comfortable properties. Organic cotton ensures user comfort by effectively maintaining body temperature, referring to findings in a study on the insulation value of sleeping bag systems (Zuo, 2004).

The Cozy Wrap heating system relies on a biodegradable heat pack consisting of iron powder, salt, and water. The pack is placed in a special pocket inside the sleeping bag, providing the necessary warmth in low-temperature situations. This is consistent with studies on thermal protection capabilities in modular systems (Hickey & Petersen, 1994) and approaches to sustainable design involving biodegradable materials (Mak et al., 2011).

In the insulation layer, fatty acids are added to increase the thermal insulation ability of the sleeping bag. These fatty acids help improve insulation ability, which is consistent with studies on thermal insulation and thermal requirements (Zuo, 2004).

The outer skin of the sleeping bag uses nylon or polyester material, which provides additional protection against harsh environmental factors, as suggested in studies on biodiversity and threats in marine areas (Marine Caves, 2004). A flexible plastic bag is used to wrap the heat pack, ensuring easy storage and use, in line with the standard of environmentally friendly materials recommended in sustainable design (Kim, 2010).

The entire Cozy Wrap design involves an additional layer of insulation which is critical in ensuring optimal insulation performance. With the combination of these materials, Cozy Wrap not only offers excellent comfort and thermal protection but also emphasizes sustainability and suitability for the maritime environment, following research on rescue technology in polar regions (Mak et al., 2011).

3. FINDINGS

Cozy Wrap offers innovative solutions specifically designed to meet the heating needs of maritime environments, utilizing environmentally friendly materials and advanced thermal insulation technology. The findings assess the effectiveness of the design, the materials used, and how it overcomes the challenge of heating in extreme temperature and high humidity situations.

3.1 Thermal Insulation Effectiveness

Preliminary findings show that the use of organic cotton in the inner layer of Cozy Wrap provides high comfort and effective insulation capabilities. Organic cotton ensures that the user's body temperature remains stable and comfortable even in cold conditions, which is supported by studies on the insulating value of sleeping bag systems (Zuo, 2004). In addition, the outer layer made of recycled polyester proved to work well in protecting against moisture and harsh environmental factors, which is consistent with findings about the durability of the material in a maritime context (Mak et al., 2011). A study on modular systems also showed that the addition of fatty acids in the insulation layer increased the sleeping bag's ability to maintain a comfortable temperature, confirming results from studies of thermal insulation in sleeping systems (Hickey & Petersen, 1994).

3.2.2 Impact of Environmental Sustainability and Safety

The findings show that the biodegradable heat pack used in the Cozy Wrap complies with the sustainability principles established by sustainable design studies (Kim, 2010). The pack consists of natural materials that are easily decomposed and safe for the environment, ensuring environmentally friendly use and reducing the ecological impact. Sleeping bag outer skins that use polyester or nylon also help reduce the need for non-recyclable materials, supporting sustainability practices in maritime product design (Marine Caves, 2004). The overall design and use of materials in the Cozy Wrap ensure that this product not only performs well in extreme conditions but also complies with strict environmental standards.

4. DISCUSSION

This data from Figure 2-6 shows that although existing sleeping bags already meet most user needs, there is room for improvement. Focusing on improving thermal insulation, making the design lighter and more compact, and improving waterproof features can improve the user experience better. This goes along with the suggestion that the interior comfort aspect also remains a key feature that should be taken care of.

Have you ever used a sleeping bag before?
100 responses

Figure 2: Have you ever used a sleeping bag?

If yes, how would you rate your overall experience with sleeping bags?
63 responses

Figure 3: If yes, how would you rate your overall experience with sleeping bags?

How effective do you find the sleeping bag in maintaining warmth during use?
100 responses

Figure 4: How effective do you find the sleeping bag in maintaining warmth during use?

Which feature of the sleeping bag do you find most valuable?
100 responses

Figure 5: Which feature of the sleeping bag do you find most valuable?

What improvements or additional features would you like to see in future versions of the sleeping bag?
100 responses

Figure 6: What improvements or additional features would you like to see in future versions of the sleeping bag?

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study found that although users are generally satisfied with the existing sleeping bag, several aspects require improvement, especially in terms of thermal insulation, a more compact and lightweight design, as well as better waterproof features. The comfort of the inner layer is the most appreciated feature, but users also emphasize the importance of durability and thermal insulation function in the product. Therefore, to meet the growing needs of consumers, manufacturers can consider these recommendations to improve the quality and performance of sleeping bags in the future, while providing a more satisfying experience and meeting the needs of various weather conditions.

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